

Leveraging a Neural-Symbolic Representation of Biomedical Knowledge to Improve Pediatric Subphenotyping

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Introduction

Subphenotyping aims to cluster patients with a particular disease into clinically distinct groups. Genomic and related molecular signatures, such as mRNA expression, have recently shown great promise for subphenotyping¹, but such molecular data are not available for most patients. Linking knowledge from generalized molecular data to patient observations may help solve this problem until molecular data is available for every patient. Biomedical ontologies, when integrated into a knowledge graph (KG), provide a biologically meaningful representation of molecular mechanism(s). Deep learning has recently demonstrated promise when used to reduce complex KGs² and have been successfully applied to embed electronic health record (EHR) data for phenotyping³. It is currently unknown if embedding knowledge of molecular mechanism(s) at the patient-level, would improve subphenotyping.

To address this gap, we leverage neural-symbolic representation learning of a biomedical KG to generate molecular mechanism embeddings associated with human disease. These embeddings are then mapped to a patient's conditions, medications, and labs from an EHR. *We hypothesize that mapping each patient's unique sets of conditions, medications, and labs to the molecular mechanism(s) will improve subphenotyping.* As a proof-of-concept, we demonstrate how this approach performs on a multiclass classification task compared to embeddings derived using only clinical concepts.

Methods

Subjects: we examined two groups of pediatric patients: (1) Rare Disease Patients (≥ 10 visits) with a diagnosis of Phenylketonuria (PKU), Congenital Hypothyroidism (CH), Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), or Cystic Fibrosis (CF); (2) Other Patients with similarly medically complex records (≥ 10 visits) and no occurrence of the diagnosis codes used to identify Rare Disease Patients.

Clinical Data: patient data were extracted from a de-identified version of the Childrens Hospital Colorado EHR. All data from the condition occurrence, drug exposure, measurement, and visit occurrence tables were considered. Use of this data was approved by the Colorado Multiple Institutional Review Board (15-0445).

Molecular Data: a KG was built using Semantic Web technologies that included phenotypes, diseases, genes, biological processes, molecular functions, cellular components, pathways, and chemicals. Data sources used to construct the KG included: the Human Phenotype Ontology (HP), the Gene Ontology, the Human Disease Ontology (DOID), Reactome, the Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (CTD), and the STRING Database (downloaded 11/2017).

Embeddings. Clinical: patient-level embeddings were generated using (Doc2Vec5, Python Gensim library). Both the distributed memory model (DM) and distributed bag of words (DBOW) models were applied. For each model, different combinations of sliding window size (5, 10, 15, 20) and dimensions (100, 150, 200) were examined. A bag-of-words model with term-frequency inverse document frequency was used as the baseline representation.

Mechanism: embeddings were generated from the biomedical KG edge list using a modified version of the DeepWalk algorithm. DeepWalk generate paths of mechanism(s) from the KG (e.g. CFTR *has function* chloride transmembrane transport) and then learns embeddings of these paths using a skip-gram like approach (parameters: 512 dimensions, sliding window size of 10). Patient-level mechanism(s) embeddings are derived (after mechanism(s) are mapped to clinical concepts) by averaging each patient's set of mapped mechanism(s) embeddings.

Terminology Mapping. Mappings were made between: (1) conditions (i.e. SNOMED-CT codes) and the HP/DOID concepts, (2) medications (i.e. RxNorm codes) and Mesh identifiers from the CTD, and (3) laboratory tests (i.e. LOINC codes) and HP/DOID concepts. For medications and diagnoses, the following steps were used to map medical codes to ontology concepts: 1) retrieve ontology and/or database cross-references; 2) exact string-match code labels to ontology and/or database labels and synonyms; and 3) manually mapping. For laboratory tests, clinically abnormal results (i.e. results above or below a specified reference range) were mapped to HP concepts.

Evaluation. A one-vs-the-rest multiclass classification strategy, with five cross-fold validation, was used to evaluate the discriminatory ability two types of embeddings: 1) clinical embeddings (i.e. generating embeddings using only condition, medication, and laboratory test codes); 2) mechanism embeddings (i.e. the average of all mechanism embeddings that were successfully mapped to each patients clinical codes). To account for for class imbalance, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling with Edited Nearest Neighbors under-sampling was implemented⁴. Classifiers included: logistic regression, Bernoulli Naïve Bayes, and a Linear Support Vector Machine. Precision and recall were used to evaluate performance. Embeddings from the best performing models were dimensionality reduced using the t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding algorithm and visualized. Rare Disease Patient Subphenotype differences were investigated using K-Means clustering and reviewed with a clinician.

Results

Eligible patients included 2,464 Rare Disease Patients (CF=835, CH=760, SCD=816, and PKU=235) and 10,000 Other Patients. Clinical embeddings were built from 178,727 visits and included 6,382 conditions, 2,334 medications, and 272 labs. Mechanism(s) embeddings were generated from a KG comprised of 116,158 nodes (human genes (n=23,776), diseases (n=3,744), GO concepts (n=49,185), phenotypes (n=13,159), pathways (n=11,124), and chemicals (n=15,019)) and 3,593,567 edges. Successful mappings of mechanism(s) were made for 45.4% (n=2900) of conditions, 99.7% (n=2327) of medications, and 72.2% (n=130) of labs. It is important to note that only 180 of the available 272 labs had valid results and were thus eligible for this mapping (n=180).

For all embeddings, the Linear Support Vector Machine classifier performed best. The best performance for the DM (precision=0.77, recall=0.75) and DBOW (precision=0.83, recall=0.82) models occurred with 150 dimensions and a sliding window size of 5. The averaged mechanism(s) embeddings (precision=0.95, recall=0.95) out-performed all parameterizations of the Doc2Vec models. Clustering the Rare Disease Patient's embeddings from the DBOW model (150, 5) resulted in 6 clusters (i.e. 1 CF, 1 SCD, 1 CH, and 3 mixed disease). In comparison, clustering the averaged mechanism embeddings resulted in 10 clusters (2 CF, 3 CH, 3 SCD, 1 PKU, and 1 mixed disease).

Conclusion

This work describes preliminary results from leveraging neural-symbolic representation learning of a biomedical KG to generate patient-level mechanism(s) embeddings. Our findings demonstrate superior performance of these embeddings compared to embeddings learned using only clinical data. Clustering the embeddings from the best performing models resulted in promising rare disease subphenotypes suggestive of different stages of each disease. Future work will address existing limitations by validating results using data from a different EHR, exploring alternatives for balancing data, and examining different classifiers.

References

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